

where E_1^A, E_2^A and E_1^B, E_2^B the molar extinction coefficients for Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes at 640 nm and 600 nm respectively are $170(E_1^A)$, $125(E_2^A)$, $84(E_1^B)$ and $70(E_2^B)$ $\text{l mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The results for the determination of Cu(II) and Ni(II) in synthetic mixtures of the two are quite satisfactory.

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Bromatometric Estimation of Ascorbic Acid Using Azine and Oxazine Dyes as Indicators[†]

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THE indicators that have been reported for the bromatometric estimation of ascorbic acid are: *p*-ethoxychrysoidine¹; starch-iodide², aminophenoxazines³, naphthol blue black and variamine blue⁴, and chlorpromazine, promazine, perazine and diethazine⁵. Of these, only *p*-ethoxychrysoidine has been utilised for the titrimetric determination of ascorbic acid in the pure form as well as medicinal preparations¹. The present communication describes the use of eleven azine

and oxazine dyes, Neutral Violet(NV), Neutral Red(NR), Azocarmine G (ACG), Azocarmine B (ACB), Wool Fast Blue GL (WFBGL), Nigrosin (NG), Capri Blue (CB), Solochrome Prune AS (SPAS), Gallamine Blue (GB), Celestine Blue (CLB), and Meldola's Blue (MB) (Colour Index Nos. 50030, 50040, 50085, 50090, 50320, 50420, 51015, 51040, 51045, 51050 and 51175 respectively), as indicators in the titrimetric estimation of ascorbic acid with potassium bromate in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media and the application of the methods for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial vitamin C tablets. In this connection, it may be mentioned that the azine dyes have been used for the titration of arsenic (III) with potassium bromate⁶.

The advantages of the indicators now reported are: (1) they can be added at the beginning of the titration, (2) the titration can be performed even in the absence of added potassium bromide, and (3) three of the indicators, ACG, ACB and WFBGL, function reversibly and can therefore be employed for the reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of potassium bromate with ascorbic acid, also; the indicators reported earlier have to be added towards the close of the titration, presence of added potassium bromide is necessary, and except variamine blue, other indicators are not suitable for the reverse titrations.

Experimental

Approximately 0.1*N* solutions of potassium bromate and ascorbic acid were prepared and standardised. A small quantity (0.5 g per litre) of E.D.T.A. was added as stabiliser for the ascorbic acid solutions. Solutions (0.1%) of the azine and oxazine dyes were prepared in deionised water from the following samples: NV: George T. Gurr, NR: E. Merck, ACG and NG: Fluka, WFBGL: Bayer, CB: Chroma, ACB, SPAS, GB, CLB and MB: E. Gurr.

Procedure:

Ascorbic acid solution (3–10 ml of 0.1 *N*) is treated with enough 1:1 hydrochloric or sulphuric acid, so as to give an acidity of 1.0*M* hydrochloric acid or 2.5*M* (3.0 with SPAS, CB and GB) sulphuric acid when diluted to 50 ml, and the following amount of the indicator solution:

NR, ACG, WFBGL, CB, SPAS, GB and MB: 0.1 ml, ACB and NG: 0.25 ml, NV and CLB: 0.5 ml.

The mixture is then titrated with 0.1 *N* potassium bromate solution and the end point is indicated by the decolourisation of the titration mixture.

The colour changes at the end points are very sharp and the results obtained are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other methods.

The following indicators function satisfactorily in titrations involving dilute (0.01*N*) solutions of ascorbic acid and potassium bromate also.

[†] Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, Waltair, December 27-31, 1978.

HCl medium : (1.0M) : NV, NR, ACG, ACB, WFBGL, CB, SPAS, CLB, GB and MB.

H₂SO₄ medium : (1.0M) + 5 ml of 10% KBr solution : NV, NR, WFBGL, CLB, SPAS and GB

NG does not function satisfactorily in any acid medium.

Titrations of 0.1N solutions do not require any indicator correction whereas those involving 0.01N solutions require the following indicator corrections :

HCl medium : NV, NR, ACG, ACB and WFBGL : 0.02 ml ; CB : 0.04 ml ; GB : 0.06 ml ; SPAS, CLB and MB : 0.10 ml

H₂SO₄ medium : NV, NR, WFBGL and CLB : 0.04 ml ; SPAS and GB : 0.10 ml.

Reverse titrations : Variamine blue⁷ is the only indicator proposed for the reverse titrations, i. e., titrations of potassium bromate with ascorbic acid. Our investigations have shown that ACG, ACB and WFBGL can be satisfactorily employed in the titrations of potassium bromate with ascorbic acid in 1.5 - 1.75M sulphuric acid medium. In these titrations, the indicator has to be added towards the close of the titration, and waiting for about 30-40 sec is necessary in the vicinity of the end point. The end point is taken as that at which the colour of the dye, pink with ACG and ACB and blue with WFBGL, is imparted to the titration mixture and is stable for more than 30 sec.

Attempts to perform the reverse titrations in hydrochloric acid medium yielded erratic results.

Mechanism of indicator action ; The functioning of the indicators in these titrations can be explained to be due to the bromination of the dye indicators, in view of the liberation of bromine and discharge of the colours of the dyes at the end points. Separate experiments have indicated that these dyes get decolourised by bromination. Further support to this mechanism is provided by the work of Bogнар⁸ involving the use of the azine dyes, Azocarmine B, Azocarmine BX, Azocarmine G, Azocarmine GX, Rosindulin G, Rosindulin GG, and Rosindulin 2G, as indicators in the titration of arsenic (III) and antimony (III) with a solution of bromine.

In view of the advantages associated with the use of the azine and oxazine dye indicators in the bromatometric titrations of ascorbic acid, we have applied the methods now developed for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial vitamin C tablets. Solutions of the tablets were prepared as described in an earlier method⁹ and aliquots of the solutions were titrated with 0.1N potassium bromate solution using any one of the azine and oxazine dye indicators. A similar aliquot was titrated using *p*-ethoxychrysoidine as indicator as

per the method of Schulek *et al*¹. Typical results obtained are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - DETERMINATION OF ASCORBIC ACID IN VITAMIN C TABLETS

Indicator and amount of ascorbic acid found, in g, in 6 tablets ^φ		
Schulek's method ¹	ACG ^α	SPAS ^α
2.95 ± 0.01	2.95 ± 0.01	2.95 ± 0.01
2.97 ± 0.01	2.98 ± 0.01	2.98 ± 0.01
3.10 ± 0.01	3.09 ± 0.01	3.10 ± 0.01
2.94 ± 0.01	2.94 ± 0.01	2.93 ± 0.01

^φ These were market products of different manufacturers.
^α Similar results were obtained with the remaining nine indicators also.

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Spectrophotometric Microgram Determination of Lead

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EXTENSIVE work on the determination of lead present as contamination has been carried out by various workers¹⁻⁴. Lead as usual with other metals becomes toxic in nature beyond certain conce-

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